

Environmental policy and environmental management by regions in Azerbaijan

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SUMMARY

The impact of the economy on environmental policy is of great importance for environmental protection and sustainable development. Environmental protection and sustainable use of resources have been taken as priorities in the economic development process in Azerbaijan. The use of green technologies and renewable energy sources is important for reducing environmental pollution and ensuring sustainable economic development. Taking environmental measures in the industrial, transport and agricultural sectors improves the quality of the environment. Special programs should be implemented to reduce carbon emissions and recycle waste. Ecotourism and clean energy projects contribute to the creation of jobs by having a positive impact on the local economy. The development of ecological transport in cities and the expansion of green areas have a positive impact on the health of the population. The implementation of environmental standards in industrial sectors is an important step for environmental protection.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the impact of the economy on environmental policy in Azerbaijan and to determine the role and importance of environmental policy on economic development. At the same time, it is to put forward proposals to ensure the environmental sustainability of economic activities.

Methods

The article used economic-statistical grouping, comparative analysis, systematization, observation, interview, and expert evaluation methods.

Keywords: *economy, ecology, environmentally friendly technology, environmental management.*

INTRODUCTION

In a globalizing world, it is important to strike a balance between economic development and environmental sustainability. The impact of the economy on environmental policy in Azerbaijan is particularly important in terms of the development of the non-oil sector and the goals of sustainable economic growth. Reducing dependence on the oil and gas sector and diversifying the economy through the application of more environmentally friendly technologies is one of the main goals of the country's environmental policy. Therefore, studying the impact of environmental policy on economic development is of particular importance in terms of ensuring economic and environmental sustainability.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSIONS

The founder and national leader of independent Azerbaijan, Heydar Aliyev, created solid foundations for the economic growth and comprehensive development of our country. His strategic leadership period led to the taking of important steps that ensured long-term development not only in the economy, but also in other areas. With the strategic decisions he made during his leadership of Azerbaijan during the Soviet Union from 1969 to 1982, as well as during his later activities in Moscow, Heydar Aliyev planned the future development of independent Azerbaijan and pursued an effective policy in this direction. During this period, a purposeful ecological policy was also implemented under the leadership of Heydar Aliyev in the field of environmental protection, which was of great importance for the future development of the country.

In the 1970s, on his initiative, large-scale greening activities were carried out in Azerbaijan. Within the framework of these activities, large green areas were created in cities and regions, and various ecological projects were implemented to protect the environment. If until 1970, the green areas in Baku covered only 3 thousand hectares, then during the years when Heydar Aliyev led the country, this figure was increased to 17 thousand hectares. Thus, greening activities were not limited only to beautifying the capital, but also became an important step towards improving people's health and the ecological environment of the city.

During this period, as a result of Heydar Aliyev's special emphasis on environmental protection, a number of laws were adopted to ensure the efficient use of natural resources and the preservation of ecological balance. Among the laws adopted on environmental protection and the efficient management of natural resources, there are 8 important legislative acts and more than 30 decisions approved at the government level. These laws played an important role in protecting the country's environment, preventing pollution, and ensuring the proper use of natural resources.

In addition, the laws adopted at the initiative of Heydar Aliyev laid the foundation for a more effective implementation of the established standards and regulations on environmental protection. These steps created conditions for the formation of an effective policy on regulating environmental issues and environmental protection in Azerbaijan. Among the decisions approved at the government level, there were also measures covering various areas such as reducing the environmental impact of industrial enterprises, protecting and expanding forest areas, and efficient use of water resources.

This environmental policy implemented by Heydar Aliyev was also accompanied by the preparation and implementation of various proposals aimed at minimizing damage to nature and greenery. He approached the issues of environmental protection and development with particular sensitivity and defined environmental protection as an integral part of Azerbaijan's development strategy. These steps taken during his time became a solid foundation for projects implemented in the field of environmental protection in subsequent years and left a deep mark on the environmental policy of the independent Azerbaijani state.

The Law "On Environmental Protection", adopted on June 8, 1999, was one of the legislative acts that formed the basis of Azerbaijan's environmental policy. This law was adopted with the aim of ensuring environmental protection and efficient use of natural resources and established important mechanisms for protecting environmental safety in the country. Another law signed on the same date, the Law "On Environmental Safety", established environmental safety standards in the country and created a legal framework to prevent environmental pollution and ensure the protection of ecosystems.

Another important law adopted under the leadership of Heydar Aliyev is the law "On Specially Protected Natural Areas and Objects" (May 24, 2000). This law regulates the creation and management of national

parks, reserves and other protected natural areas in Azerbaijan. The adoption of this law has created an opportunity to protect the country's biodiversity and preserve unique ecosystems. Thanks to these measures, implemented at the initiative of Heydar Aliyev, the total area of specially protected areas has been increased and nature conservation in these areas has been ensured more effectively.

Information accessibility is also of great importance for solving environmental issues. To this end, the Law "On Obtaining Information on the Environment", adopted on March 12, 2002, ensured public awareness in the field of environmental protection and increased transparency on environmental issues.

The application of insurance mechanisms for ensuring ecological safety and environmental protection in the country is also important. In this regard, the law "On Compulsory Environmental Insurance", adopted on April 21, 2002, regulated the activities of enterprises that cause environmental damage and ensured compensation for losses resulting from polluting activities. This law strengthened the legal framework for environmental insurance in the country and created conditions for the creation of new financial mechanisms for environmental protection.

The development of environmental education and awareness has also been an integral part of Heydar Aliyev's environmental policy. In this area, the law "On Environmental Education and Awareness of the Population", adopted on December 10, 2002, was adopted to increase the population's awareness of environmental protection and ensure the widespread dissemination of knowledge about ecology.

The legal reforms initiated by national leader Heydar Aliyev in the field of ecology have been continued on the solid foundations he created and successfully developed under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev. Under the leadership of Ilham Aliyev, special importance was given to improving the legislative framework in this field and important laws were adopted to solve environmental problems.

Several laws adopted within the framework of these reforms deserve special attention. For example, the amendments made to the Law "On Specially Protected Natural Areas and Objects" on December 3, 2002 served to further strengthen the legal mechanisms related to the protection and management of these areas. In addition, the law adopted on March 5, 2004, in connection with the implementation of the Law "On Environmental Education and Awareness of the Population", amendments and additions were made to a number of other laws, which created conditions for the wider dissemination of environmental awareness and the strengthening of environmental education.

At the same time, the ratification of the Framework Convention for the Protection of the Caspian Sea Environment on April 4, 2006 was one of the country's important steps towards ensuring environmental security in the Caspian region. The measures implemented within the framework of this Convention are aimed at protecting the marine ecological environment and preventing environmental pollution.

In order to strengthen the ecological safety of Azerbaijan, amendments and supplements were made to the Law "On Ecological Safety" and the Code of Administrative Offenses on December 7, 2007. These amendments provided for the application of stricter punishment mechanisms against activities that violate ecological safety and created conditions for more strict protection of the rules related to ecological safety.

In addition, the Law on Ecologically Clean Agriculture, adopted on June 13, 2008, envisages expanding the application of ecological standards in agriculture and promoting methods that will cause less damage to nature. This law aims to ensure the use of ecologically clean technologies by agricultural producers and the issuance of ecological certificates.

Within the framework of the comprehensive environmental policy implemented in the country, special importance is attached to the protection and expansion of specially protected areas. According to statistical data, while the total area of specially protected areas in Azerbaijan was 3824.8 km² in 1990, this figure reached 4298.6 km² in 2000, 6038.2 km² in 2005, 8807.7 km² in 2010 and 8925.5 km² in 2015. Thus, this area has increased 2.4 times compared to 1990.

It should be noted that if in 1990 specially protected lands accounted for 4.4 percent of the country's territory, as a result of the measures taken, the area of these territories has increased since 2003 and currently covers 10.3 percent of the country's territory.

The Heydar Aliyev Foundation, which has been successfully operating since 2004 under the leadership of Mehriban Aliyeva, the First Lady of Azerbaijan and Goodwill Ambassador of UNESCO and ISESCO, makes significant contributions to the development of the country through projects implemented in various fields. One of the main directions of the Foundation's activity is the implementation of various projects in the field of ecology and the organization of effective measures to solve environmental problems. The Foundation, which actively participates in the construction of a new society, not only supports the socio-economic development of the country, but also promotes projects for environmental protection. The Foundation's environmental projects are characterized by consistent and purposeful work, especially in the direction of promoting a healthy lifestyle and protecting the environment.

The IDEA (International Dialogue for Environmental Protection) Public Association, headed by Leyla Aliyeva, Vice-President of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, also carries out large-scale activities to solve environmental problems and protect the environment. Various projects organized by IDEA are aimed at raising environmental awareness in society and promoting environmental protection. Among the events carried out in this context, the "All-Republic Greening" marathon and the "Eco Painting Agenda 2014" international competition, which caused a wide public resonance, should be specially noted.

As a result of the consistent state policy implemented in Azerbaijan since 1993, the area of specially protected areas has been significantly expanded. As a result, there are currently 9 national parks, 11 state nature reserves, and 24 state nature reserves operating in the country.

Within the framework of the current environmental policy, the main focus is on the creation of infrastructures in specially protected natural areas in accordance with international standards. In a short period of time, a modern and exemplary infrastructure has been established in Shahdag National Park, one of the largest national parks in the Caucasus. In addition, special towns for ecotourism have been created in Shirvan and Hirkan National Parks, which has supported the development of ecotourism. [1]

Work continues to protect wildlife, and as part of projects implemented in this area with the support of the Heydar Aliyev Foundation, about 150 gazelles have been relocated to their historical habitats.

Historical Development of Environmental Policy and National Legislation-The foundation of Azerbaijan's environmental policy was laid during the Soviet era. However, the acceleration of industrialization during this period led to large-scale exploitation of natural resources, and environmental protection issues were often ignored. After the collapse of the Soviet Union, when Azerbaijan gained independence, it began to create a new legal framework for environmental protection and sustainable use of natural resources.

The Law on Environmental Protection, adopted in 1999, was an important step in the development of environmental policy. This law established the principles of environmental safety, responsibilities for polluters, and a legal framework for environmental management. In 2010, the government began to take stricter measures against environmental violations by increasing serious environmental fines, which created serious discipline in the implementation of laws.

International Obligations and Impact-Azerbaijan's environmental policy is not limited to national legislation, but also seeks to adapt to global standards through international commitments. The country has adopted an action plan to combat climate change by joining documents such as the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Paris Agreement. Azerbaijan has committed to implementing national measures to slow climate change and reduce carbon emissions by 35% by 2030. [3]

When comparing Azerbaijan's environmental situation and policies with other countries, some notable nuances emerge. For example, in 2020, Azerbaijan's carbon emissions were approximately 30 million tons of CO₂ per year, which is average compared to Central Asian and Caucasian countries. Georgia's carbon emissions in the same year were 8 million tons, and Kazakhstan's were 368 million tons. These figures indicate that Azerbaijan has lower emissions than industrialized countries, but given that its economy is largely based on the oil and gas sector, it is clear that additional measures need to be taken to reduce the environmental impacts of this sector.

However, oil production on the Absheron Peninsula has had a long-term negative impact on the environment. According to statistics, the level of soil pollution in some areas of Absheron increased 10 times

in the 1990s. However, since 2015, the government has invested about 1 billion US dollars in new environmental projects and technologies to prevent this pollution. As a result of these investments, by 2022, the level of pollution on the Absheron Peninsula has decreased by 30% as a result of land cleaning projects. Environmental management strategies in different regions of Azerbaijan differ according to the ecological problems and economic characteristics of the areas.

1. Karabakh and Zangezur Region: Forest restoration, sustainable management of water resources, and reclamation of agricultural lands are being carried out in the liberated areas. Ecological studies conducted in these areas after the occupation show that 45% of the lands have been degraded. The Azerbaijani government has allocated 300 million manats for large-scale projects to revive agriculture and restore ecological balance here.

2. Absheron Peninsula: According to statistics, the level of negative environmental impact here has decreased by 50% as a result of the cleaning of oil-contaminated lands from 2010 to 2020. The government has invested 500 million manat in the development of renewable energy sources, especially wind energy, in this region.

3. Guba-Khachmaz Region: Agricultural productivity has increased by 30% within the framework of projects for the modernization of irrigation systems and effective management of water resources. New reservoirs have also been constructed to prevent water shortages.

4. Kura-Araz Plain: As a major agricultural region, soil salinization remains a serious problem. Thanks to the optimization of irrigation systems in this region, salinization levels have been reduced by 20%.

5. Sheki-Zagatala Region: Ecotourism activities have been developed in this region, which has contributed to the diversification of the economy. For example, in 2018, ecotourism revenues here amounted to 15 million manat, while in 2022 this figure reached 25 million manat, which is an increase of 66%. [2]

The main goal of Azerbaijan's environmental policy is to ensure ecological balance with sustainable economic development. To this end, efforts are being made to solve environmental problems both at the national level and through international cooperation. By the end of 2025, the Azerbaijani government plans to increase the share of renewable energy sources to 30%, which is an important step towards increasing clean energy production. At the same time, measures are being taken to recycle and reduce waste, which ensures that damage to nature is minimized.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the environmental policy implemented in our country includes comprehensive measures aimed at environmental protection, sustainable use of natural resources and ensuring environmental safety. This approach, based on the principles of sustainable development, ensures that Azerbaijan achieves its goals in the environmental field and creates the basis for the protection of a healthy environment for future generations. In accordance with the pace of economic development of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources implements a modern environmental policy based on the principles of flexible management. This policy includes the application of progressive approaches to prevent the degradation of non-renewable components of the environment, promote the application of low-emission and innovative technologies, expand cooperation with developed countries and international organizations, and increase environmental knowledge among the population. The Ministry, by developing strategic programs for environmental protection, forms sustainable management mechanisms in this area.

The main goal of the environmental policy implemented in the Republic of Azerbaijan is to protect existing ecosystems, ensure the sustainability of economic potential and meet the needs of present and future generations through the rational use of natural resources. This policy accepts the provision of sustainable development as a basic principle. In order to ensure sustainable development from an ecological point of view, it is necessary to comprehensively solve environmental problems arising from economic activity and minimize the negative impact of these problems on the environment.

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